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1 МАХСУС СОН

ЎЗБЕКСКИЙ МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ
СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 1

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A NEW APPROACH TO THE TREATMENT OF TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS WITH CORONARY HEART DISEASE

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ABSTRACT

In modern clinical practice, type 2 diabetes mellitus therapy should be aimed not only at achieving glycemic control, but also at influencing other modified risk factors for the development of cardiovascular diseases, including hypertension, overweight, frequent hypoglycemia, etc. [4]. Empagliflozin is the first hypoglycemic drug for which a new indication has been approved for use as a means to reduce the risk of cardiovascular mortality in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and concomitant cardiovascular diseases.

Keywords: type 2 diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular complications, empagliflozin.

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НОВЫЙ ПОДХОД ЛЕЧЕНИЯ САХАРНОГО ДИАБЕТА 2-го ТИПА С ИШЕМИЧЕСКОЙ БОЛЕЗНЬЮ СЕРДЦА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В современной клинической практике терапия сахарного диабета 2-го типа должна быть направлена не только на достижение контроля гликемии, но и на воздействие на другие модифицированные факторы риска развития сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний, включающие в себя артериальную гипертензию, избыточную массу тела, частые гипогликемии и т. д. [4]. Эмпаглифлозин является первым сахароснижающим препаратом, для которого одобрено новое показание использования как средства, уменьшающего риск сердечно-сосудистой смертности у пациентов с сахарным диабетом 2-го типа и сопутствующими сердечно-сосудистыми заболеваниями.

Ключевые слова: сахарный диабет 2-го типа, сердечно-сосудистые осложнения, эмпаглифлозин.

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Бухоро давлат тиббиёт институти жаррохлик касалликлар
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ЮРАК ИШЕМИК КАСАЛЛИГИ БИЛАН ҚАНДЛИ ДИАБЕТНИНГ 2-ТУРИДА ДАВОЛАШДА ЯНГИ ЁНДАШУВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Замонавий клиник амалиётда қандли диабет 2- турининг терапияси нафақат гликемик назоратга эришишга, балки юрак-қон томир касалликлари, шу жумладан гипертония, ортиқча вазн, тез-тез гипогликемия ва бошқалар ривожланиши учун бошқа ўзгартирилган хавф омилларига таъсир кўрсатишга қаратилган бўлиши керак. [4]. Эмпаглифлозин биринчи гипогликемик дори бўлиб, унинг учун 2-тоифа қандли диабет ва юрак-қон томир касалликлари билан оғриган беморларда юрак-қон томир ўлими хавфини камайтириш воситаси сифатида фойдаланиш учун янги кўрсаткич тасдиқланган.

Калит сўзлар: 2-тоифа қандли диабет, юрак-қон томир асоратлари, эмпаглифлозин.

Introduction: It is a well-known fact that type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM2) is an independent risk factor for the development of cardiovascular (SS) complications, and is also considered as equivalent to the presence of a clinically pronounced cardiovascular disease (CVD) in a patient. According to the results of the epidemiological study NATION conducted by the Federal State Budgetary Institution "Endocrinological Research Center" of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation in the period from 2013 to 2015, it was revealed that the true number of DM patients in Russia is approximately 2 times more than the officially registered one and reaches 7 million people, which is about 5.4% of the population [1].

In 60-75% of cases, CVD is the cause of deaths in patients with DM2 [2, 3], which indicates the need to pay special attention to this problem. In modern clinical practice, DM2 therapy should be aimed not only at achieving glycemic control, but also at influencing other modified risk factors for the development of CVD, including hypertension, overweight, frequent hypoglycemia, etc. [4].

It is no secret that many hypoglycemic drugs have a high potential for reducing HbA1c levels. Taking into account the complex pathophysiological links between DM2, obesity, hypertension and atherosclerosis, not only their ability to provide glycemic control, but also their influence on SS risk factors in patients with DM2 is of particular importance for all available in practice and emerging new hypoglycemic agents [5-7].

Increased glucose reabsorption in the kidneys is an important pathogenetic mechanism supporting chronic hyperglycemia in DM2. About 90% of glucose is reabsorbed in the proximal renal tubule by type 2 sodium-glucose transporters (NGL-2/SGLT-2), and the remaining 10% by type 1 glucose transporters (NGL-1/SGLT-1) located distally. With DM2, the activity of the type 2 sodium-glucose cotransporter increases, the capacity of renal glucose transport increases, and, consequently, the renal glucose threshold increases [8-10].

Gliflozines inhibit SGLT-2, which causes a decrease in the reabsorption of sodium and glucose from the lumen of the proximal renal tubule and leads to the development of glucosuria (Fig. 1). As a result, about 60-90 g of glucose is excreted in urine per day, which creates an energy deficit of about 300 kcal. The concomitant loss of water in this case, according to clinical studies, is about 375 ml (corresponds to approximately 1.5 additional urination per day). The precursor of all drugs of the iNGLT-2 type group was florizin, obtained by French chemists in 1835 from the bark of the roots of apple trees. Back in 1886, Von Mering showed that its introduction to humans causes glucosuria, but the surge of scientific interest in florizine occurred only in the XX century. It was found that florizine is an inhibitor of both SGLT-2 and SGLT-1. In animals with DM, the use of florizine led to the development of glucosuria and normalization of glycemia, which served as the basis for the assumption that pharmacologically-induced glucosuria can become an effective strategy for the treatment of patients with DM. Despite the hypoglycemic efficacy of florizin, low bioavailability and insufficient selectivity of SGLT-2/SGLT-1, accompanied by pronounced gastrointestinal side effects, did not allow its use in clinical practice, as well as its derivatives related to O-glycosides (sergliflozin, T-1095). Candidate molecules related to C-glycosides, on the contrary, have passed the stages of programmatic clinical trials and approval for use in patients with DM2. Empagliflozin belongs to this group functions of B cells, insulin resistance and duration of diabetes. NGLT-2 inhibitors contribute

to a significant decrease in GPN, as well as postprandial glycemia. The generalized average decrease in HbA1c compared to placebo is -0.7%, however, the hypoglycemic potential increases with pronounced decompensation.

The effect of iNGLT-2 persists for a long time, while the elution effect is a serious problem for many hypoglycemic drugs. In addition to the hypoglycemic effect, iNGLT-2 improves the function of B cells (most likely as a result of a decrease in glucose toxicity) and the sensitivity of muscle tissue to insulin. So as iNGLT-2 does not suppress endogenous glucose production, and also does not stimulate insulin secretion, in general, this class is characterized by a low risk of hypoglycemia. The special pharmacological properties of its molecule cause a good clinical effect in patients with DM2; in particular, even a small concentration equal to 1.3 nmol is sufficient to inhibit the 50% activity of the enzyme SGLT2 (IC50), and the selectivity of empagliflozin with respect to SGLT2 is 5000 times higher than the selectivity of SGLT1, responsible for glucose absorption in the intestine. Inhibition of SGLT1 cotransporters may disrupt glucose absorption in the intestine (the main route of exogenous glucose into the blood), and may also cause gastrointestinal side effects (diarrhea) in some patients [11].

Empagliflozin has a prolonged half-life (10-19 hours); food intake does not affect pharmacokinetics. An essential circumstance ensuring the adherence of patients to empagliflozin therapy is the possibility of a single use of the drug (1 r / day) at a dose of 10 or 25 mg, regardless of food intake. In the course of clinical studies (CI), it was found that in patients with DM2, glucose excretion by the kidneys increased immediately after the first dose of empagliflozin, and this effect lasted for 24 hours. Empagliflozin can be used in combination with any hypoglycemic drug (combination with GLP-1 receptor agonists has not been studied), including insulin [12].

The potential of empagliflozin is not limited only to glucose homeostasis and elimination of a certain amount of it from the bloodstream.

An increase in glucose excretion and moderate osmotic diuresis induce a number of systemic effects, including those modeling CC risk factors: lowering blood pressure, reducing body weight mainly due to adipose tissue, reducing albuminuria, reducing uric acid levels, reducing the risk of hypoglycemia, improving the sensitivity of muscle tissue to insulin, etc.

Among the possible mechanisms of the hypotensive effect of gliflozines, the following are considered:

- 1) osmotic diuresis;
- 2) weight loss;
- 3) an increase in the concentration of sodium in the lumen of the tubule in the macula densa area, which can be perceived as a signal for a decrease in renin production by the cells of the juxtaglomerular apparatus;
- 4) there may be an indirect effect of nitric oxide released in response to a decrease in oxidative stress while improving glycemic control.

The decrease is more typical for systolic (-3-5 mmHg) than for diastolic (-2 mmHg) blood pressure and is more pronounced in people with high blood pressure. A recent study [13] demonstrated that empagliflozin not only lowered blood pressure, but also had a beneficial effect on markers of arterial rigidity and vascular resistance. The observation of the effect of empagliflozin on the vascular system without an increase in heart rate is of interest in the CC aspect and can be interpreted as a relative decrease in the tone of the sympathetic nervous system. It is likely that the beneficial effect of empagliflozin on reducing CC risk and HF is related to hemodynamic/CC-the effect of the drug to reduce blood pressure and intravascular volume, resulting in a combination of post- and preload reduction.

iNGLT-2 in general and empagliflozin in particular are characterized by a decrease in uric acid levels (by an average of 5.9–17.8%), depending on the severity of glucosuria. One of the proposed mechanisms is associated with a change in uric acid transport via the isoform 2 GLUT-9 (SLC2A9b). This isoform provides passive multidirectional transport of D-glucose and uric acid and, under conditions of increased glucosuria, can enhance the excretion of uric acid into the lumen of the

tubule. It is proved that the uricosuric effect of gliflozines is not associated with an increase in cases of nephrolithiasis.

A decrease in albuminuria and a decrease in the albumin/creatinine ratio in urine are characteristic of all iNGLT-2. In clinical studies of the use of gliflozines, the number of patients with progressive deterioration of the albuminuria class significantly decreased compared to placebo. With respect to renal function, the potential direct effects of iNGLT-2 are discussed: a decrease in hyperfiltration and a decrease in the activity of the local renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system, a decrease in glucose tubulotoxicity and tubular hypertrophy, an effect on the change in the balance of the tone of the fetal and excretory glomerular arterioles. However, further research in this area is required. An important distinguishing feature of SGLT2 inhibitors is their ability to reduce body weight. It is believed that inhibition of SGLT2 cotransporters leads to a loss of 60-80 g/day of glucose in urine, resulting in a negative energy balance due to a daily loss of 240-320 kcal [14, 15]. According to the results of CI, the use of empagliflozin leads to a significant decrease in the body weight of patients after 24 weeks. treatment. Moreover, the range of body weight loss is from 1.4 to 2.9 kg, depending on the duration of CI and background hypoglycemic pharmacotherapy; in particular, with longer therapy, body weight loss reaches 3.1–3.6 kg [16]. It should be noted that weight loss associated with the use of empagliflozin is maintained for a period of up to 104 weeks.

SAFETY ISSUES OF INGLT 2 APPLICATION

Urogenital infections. The presence of glucose in the urine creates favorable conditions for the reproduction of opportunistic microflora and increases the risk of genital mycotic infections (by 11% in women and 4% in men compared to placebo) and to a lesser extent - urinary tract infections. Infections in most cases of mild to moderate severity, respond well to standard treatment, cases of discontinuation of medications for this reason are very rare. In most cases, there was only one episode. In the first 1-3 weeks. the use of gliflozines may result in a transistor reduction of GFR, followed by its recovery and long-term stabilization. However, in patients with reduced renal function, the risk of increased levels of creatinine, phosphorus, parathyroid hormone, hypovolemia and arterial hypotension increases. In individuals with a filtration rate of <60 ml/min, the frequency of fractures may increase. The effect on bone metabolism in elderly patients continues to be studied. In most studies, there was a very small but statistically significant increase in HDL and LDL levels. As part of the active post-marketing surveillance of people taking drugs from the iNGLT-2 group, 101 cases of ketoacidosis have been recorded in the world to date. A causal relationship between ketoacidosis and glyphlozine intake has not been established. Concomitant factors contributing to the development of ketoacidosis were often identified: infections, injuries, urosepsis, restriction of food and water, reduction of insulin doses or alcohol intake. There have been cases of iNGLT-2 being taken by persons with DM1 and in the absence of DM. A feature of ketoacidosis on the background of iNGLT-2 is its development at relatively low values of glycemia. At the moment, in patients taking iNGLT-2 and complaining of shortness of breath, nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, fatigue and drowsiness, it is advisable to determine the level of ketones and, if ketoacidosis is confirmed, cancel the drug.

The creation and introduction into practice of inhibitors that suppress renal glucose reabsorption is a turning point in the treatment of DM2, which is largely due to their effect on CC risks. When empagliflozin was approved for the treatment of DM2 in 2014, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) required an additional post-marketing study to assess its CC safety. The EMPA-REG Outcome study is an international prospective placebo-controlled clinical trial of the CC safety of empagliflozin, a type 2 sodium-glucose cotransporter inhibitor (SGLT2) in patients with DM2 and established CVD. This is the first study to demonstrate the ability of a hypoglycemic drug to reduce the number of CC events in patients with DM2.

Conclusion. This study demonstrated the SS-safety of mpagliflozin. There was no increase in cases of hypoglycemia. In addition, the incidence of hyper- or normoglycemic ketoacidosis was very low and was not higher in patients receiving empagliflozin (0.035%) compared with placebo (0.020%) [15].

SGLT2 inhibitors quickly took a prominent place in the pharmacotherapy of DM2. Their rapid recognition is evidenced by the fact that in 2015 SGLT2 inhibitors were included in the Algorithms

of AACE (The American Association of Clinical Endocrinologists) as the preferred class for monotherapy, double and triple therapy of DM2 [14]. The class of SGLT2 inhibitors entered the Russian algorithms in February 2015. According to the 2017 ADA recommendations, metformin remains the first-line drug of therapy, and if the target level of HbA1c is not reached after 3 months. It is advisable to consider the addition of one of the following drugs: iDPP-4, aGPP-1, PSM, thiazolidinediones, basal insulin or sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitors (iNGLT-2) [9] In principle, all drugs with proven safety can be used in patients with DM2 in the presence of CVD [10]. However, to reduce the number of CC events and deaths, preference should be given to drugs with proven CC benefits. Therefore, given the convincing arguments of a favorable influence on SS events, including CHF, selective inhibitors of the type 2 sodium-glucose cotransporter, primarily empagliflozin, should be considered this group of hypoglycemic drugs as the first line, along with metformin, in the treatment of very high-risk DM2 patients, including in the presence of CHF, as noted in the new European guidelines on CHF [15], as well as in the recently published clinical guidelines of the Canadian Diabetes Association [16].

References.

1. Rizayeva Malika Jamolovna. "IMPROVEMENT OF METHODS OF TREATMENT OF PERSISTENT ATRIAL FIBRILLATION IN PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE", IEJRD Journal, vol. 5, no. SPECIAL ISSUE, p. 7, Dec. 2020.
2. Pulatova Sh.Kh. Method of improving vasopressor therapy for acute myocardial infarction complicated with cardiogenic shock 911. American Journal of Medicine and Medicine Sciences 2020. Vol.10. ISSN: 2165-901X <http://journal.sapub.org/ajmms>
3. Rizaeva, M. J., & Tukhtaev, D. A. (2020). FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH THE CRISIS COURSE OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION. In Botkin readings (pp. 227-227).
4. Rizaeva, M. J. (2020). EFFICACY AND SAFETY OF ELECTRIC CARDIOVERSION IN PERSISTENT ATRIAL FIBRILLATION. New Day in Medicine, (4), pp.322-325.
5. Rizaeva, M. Z. (2022). The clinical course of atrial fibrillation in patients with coronary heart disease. European journal of molecular medicine, 2(1).
6. Pulatova Sh.H. Improvement of treatment of patients with acute heart failure, a comparative evaluation of the effectiveness of dobutamine and levosimendan// World Journal Of Pharmaceutical Research. 2020. Vol 9 (6). – pp. 2283-2288
7. Pulatova Sh.H. Method of improving vasopressor therapy for acute myocardial infarction complicated with cardiogenic shock // American Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences. 2020.– Vol. 10 (11). – pp. 911-913
8. Pulatova Sh.Kh. Features of TLT in patients with acute myocardial infarction // Emergency Medicine Bulletin, Tashkent, 2019. - No. 6. - pp.89-92 (14.00.00; No. 11)
9. Pulatova Sh.Kh. "OPTIMIZATION OF CARDIOGENIC SHOCK TREATMENT." Uzbek Medical Journal 3.6 (2022).
10. Akhmedov L.A., Pulatova Sh. H. Optimization of hemodynamic diagnosis of acute left ventricular failure // Proceedings of the 7th Eurasian Congress of Cardiology. Cardiology of Uzbekistan. 2019, C. 255.
11. Kenjaev Jr, Akhmedov LA, Povlatova Sh, Boboeva M.M. The course of myocardial infarction in young patients // Physicians' Information Bulletin. Tashkent, 2017.- No. 4-P. 44.
12. Kenjaev Jr., Akhmedov LA, Pulatova Sh., Boboeva M.M. Complication of cardiogenic shock // Physicians' Information Bulletin on improving vasopressor therapy in the treatment of acute myocardial infarction. Tashkent, 2017.- No. 1-P. 31
13. Pulatova, Sh. H. (2012). Founders: Institute of Immunology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. THEORETICAL AND CLINICAL MEDICINE
14. Pulatova Sh.H. A method to improve vasopressor therapy of acute myocardial infarction accompanied by cardiogenic shock // American Medical Journal. 2020.- Vol. 10 (11). - - c. 911-913

15. Pulatova Sh.H. Improvement of treatment of patients with acute heart failure, comparative evaluation of dobutamine and levosimen efficacy // World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. 2020. Vol. 9 (6). - С. 2283-2288
16. Vogt A., von Essen R., Tebbe U. et al. Impact of early perfusion status of the infarct-related artery on short-term mortality after thrombolysis for acute myocardial in-farction: retrospective analysis of four German multicenter studies. // J Am Coll Cardiol 1993;21: 391—395.

ЎЗБЕК ТИББИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

1 МАХСУС СОН

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